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Research Article

**AN ANALYTICAL ANALYSIS ON COMMONNESS OF
DOMESTIC VIOLENCE AMONG MARRIED WOMEN
WORKING IN THE FIELD OF HEALTHCARE**¹Dr. Hurria Rashid, ²Dr. Rabia Ayyub, ³Dr. Kanza Yousaf¹RHC Manga Mandi Lahore²BHU 45/P, BHU 45 /P, Khanpur, Rahim Yar Khan³Medical Officer, Maroof International Hospital Islamabad**Abstract:**

Objective: The goal of our study was to guess the commonness of domestic aggression among married women healthcare provider.

Methodology: We carried out an analytical analysis at Services Hospital, Lahore (February to November 2017). Our explored findings comprised of two fifty English language quantitative article among which thirty-five became the part of this research.

Results: Analysis and scrutiny of finally selected (35) articles conclude that (10% to 69%) and (30% to 79%) is the range of domestic violence expansion in the world as well as in Pakistan respectively. The most usual category of violence is Verbal violence which subsequently leads to several different types of domestic aggression like sexual violence, physical and emotional violence etc. On the World level, availability of written material on domestic aggression among women healthcare provider is very short as well as nothing observed in form of literature with respect to Pakistan context.

Conclusion: The findings of literature analysis declare that internationally females are greatly experiencing in a huge percentage with domestic aggression as well as verbal violence is a general violence. Subsequent research regarding domestic aggression among female health care provider is most required.

Keywords: Verbal Violence, Physical and Emotional Violence, World Health Organization.

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INTRODUCTION:

Domestic violence is a worldwide public health issue. Female beyond every age, any tribe, any nation, ethnic, socio-economic, educational as well as religious grade are also at the great hazard of domestic violence [1]. Domestic violence is a main public health problem by WHO in one of his published international report on violence and health [2]. The definition of domestic violence by WHO as, an act of exploitation concerning to gender probably to result in the emotional, physical or sexual enduring of female additionally aggression blackmailing, oppressive behaviour along with deprivation of autonomy in public as well as personal life. A lot of studies presented that domestic brutality is a model of psychological, physical and inhumane treatment by an individual with whom the affected one has a very close relationship [3, 5]. Interpersonal violence, Domestic brutality, gender violence are other types of Domestic violence [6]. The other kind of domestic violence is a disparity in power-sharing between male and female. In this analytical review, the objective of the researcher is to provide diagnostic, ideological as well as an empirical review of the concerned literature to constitute the expansion of domestic violence among married women healthcare provider containing doctors along with nursing staff and debates on several kinds of exploitation including psychological, sexual, emotional and physical.

METHODOLOGY:

We carried out an analytical analysis at Services Hospital, Lahore (February to November 2017). All

the articles that are available on the internet are searched by utilizing particular keywords just like healthcare provider, domestic violence etc. All the articles regarding domestic violence included with respect to inclusion basis that they should be initiated in England and must be quantitative research.

Our explored findings comprised on 250 English language quantitative article among these 60 articles were exactly similar, the numbers of articles not fulfilling the inclusion criteria in reference with topic relevancy were 80 as well as 56 removed because of being part of the earlier published result. Leftover 19 articles were examined thoroughly and critically and depart from review because of less methodological strength. Finally, thirty-five quantitative research-based articles selected for analysis.

RESULTS:

Analysis and scrutiny of finally selected (35) articles determined that (10% to 69%) and (30% to 79%) is the range of domestic violence expansion in the world as well as in Pakistan respectively. The most usual category of violence is Verbal violence (22% to 40.1%) which subsequently leads to several different types of domestic aggression like emotional (33.8% to 83.6%), physical (16% to 70%), and sexual violence (46.9% to 76%). The ratio of domestic clash among women healthcare providers in developed as well as developing states was presented as (18% to 31%) and 39% respectively.

Table – I: Various Literary References

Author(s)	Location	Number	Detail	Number	Percentage
Shaikh, M. A. H. (2003) [5]	Islamabad and Rawalpindi	216	Increased Sex During Pregnancy	193	24.90
			Forced Sex	101	46.90
A., & Masood, Shaikh, M. A., Shaikh, I. A., Kamal, S. (2008) [21]	Islamabad and Rawalpindi	209	Physical Abuse	67	13.60
			Severe Incidents	32	47.70
			Use of Weapons	21	31.30
			Punching	3	4.50
Fikree, F. F. & Bhatti, L. I. (1999) [22]	Karachi	150	Physical Abuse	51	34.00
			Abuse During Pregnancy	23	15.00
Ali, T. S., Asad, ., Mogren, I., & Krantz, N G. (2011) [23]	Karachi	759	Past Physical Abuse	427	56.30
			Lifetime Sexual Abuse	437	57.60
			Sexual Abuse	405	53.40
			Psychological Abuse	413	54.50
Karmaliani, R., Irfan, F., Bann, C. M., McClure, E. M., Moss, N., Pasha, O., et al. (2008) [24]	Hyderabad	1324	Verbal or Physical Abuse	675	51.00
			Sexual Abuse	265	20.00
			Suicidal Cases	212	16.00
Fikree, F. F., Jafarey, S. N., Korejo, R., Khan, A., & Durocher, J. M. (2004) [25]	Karachi (Obstetricians Reports)	100	Domestic Violence Reports	70	70.00
			Physical Abuse	62	62.00
Fikree, F. F., Razzak, J. A. & Durocher, J. (2005) [26]	Karachi	176	Slapping as Physical Abuse	87	49.40
			Husband is Permitted to Abuse	81	46.00
			Hitting and Punching	84	47.70

Table – II: Under-Developed Countries Proportions about Physical Abuse

Under-Developed Countries	Physical Abuse
Pakistan	70
Thailand	20
Korea	38
India	45
Cambodia	16

DISCUSSION:

The most general phenomena by World health organization (WHO) in 2002 was violence against females. Domestic clash is one of the most prominent reason of injustice to married females in shape of domestic violence and in most cases attackers are too much closer to victim contrary to a stranger. It is obvious that two out of three females who become a victim of domestic violence knew her criminals [2].

The study carried out by WHO on 48 population-based surveys found that 10% to 69% of females all over the world have complained to have experience of mental as well as physical torture by their life partner [7]. Various studies performed in several states presented experiencing domestic clashes, containing Canada (17%), Haiti (16.4%), Bangladesh (42%) and Egypt (34%) [8 – 11]. A study which was carried out to examine expansion effects and comparison of health with martial clashes along with married discrepant in couples in the requirement of psychological treatment [12]. About 86% of the

violence reported was replacement between husband's wives, the reactions and damages sustained because of this violence as the wives got most critical injuries with respect to husbands [12].

In the USA 31% of the nurses registered complaints regarding domestic aggression experienced personally as well as by their family members [13]. In another study which was performed on 1150 nurses along with nurses' aides in Mexico City hospital, it was presented that (18% and 13%) of nurses and nurses' aides respectively got the experience of sexual or physical torture by their life partner [14]. Once more study which was carried out in South Africa by Silo, as well as Christofides in which (212) nurses were interviewed for the purpose of analysis either nurse's domestic aggression personal experience, influences their patient treatment of domestic aggression as well as rape cases. This study declares that approximately 39% of nurses were undergone emotional as well as physical, 40.6% of nurses presented that their friends and

family members become victims of domestic violence [15]. Frank and Dingle carried out a study on (2500) female physicians in the United State of America which declared that (8.8%) of the female physicians are near to death because of depression or committed suicide because of domestic aggression [16].

Domestic aggression is indigenous to Pakistan, this can be discovered by the outcomes of the USA Human Rights watch report which was published in 2006, the most comprehensive report on domestic clashes, which declared that approximately 90% of females in Pakistan were victimized to physical, verbal, emotional and sexual abuse inside their homes by their life partners [17].

The domestic aggression percentage in Pakistan is (30% to 79%) [18, 19]. According to the Human Rights Commission of Pakistan (HRCP), an annual report which was published in 2004 presented that the number of cases of verbal physical as well as sexual exploitation of females inside their own home was the highest as compared to the other countries of the world. HRCP's figures show that approximately 80% of females in Pakistan become victims of domestic violence. Moreover, the report also identified that in the first six months of 2004, almost 5464 domestic aggression cases were awaiting in Lahore civil courts, these are the cases which are registered, and the frequency of not reported cases is also massive [20]. It has also been noticed that there are larger numbers of a female who become victims of domestic aggression but they are not in a position to register their case or at least communicate their parents regarding husband behaviours [21]. As a Muslim community in Pakistan, people generally think that Islam permits a man to victimize his wife as well as to fulfil his sexual needs with his wife without her approval. Studies on several types of domestic violence tolerate by married females show the huge ratio of domestic violence in Pakistan [22 – 27].

The most general form of domestic aggression is Verbal abuse, consisting of name-calling, humiliation, yelling as well as blaming [18]. A study declared that (22%) of occurrences of verbal abuse were required conditions to harsher types of domestic violence just like sexual as well as physical abuse [28].

According to different studies, the most general kind of violence is physical abuse. Following are categories of physical violence, throwing of acid, beating, killing on the bases of honour, burning, murder and rape cases, kidnapping for the object of making prostitute. Most usual recorded injuries are a

burn of the third degree, haemorrhage of inner organs, vaginal and head injuries, asthma, depression, permanent physical impairment. Irritable bowel symptoms, sore muscles, lacerations and fractures [22, 23, 25, 29]. According to the 2002 and 2000 statistical data provided by WHO and UNICEF respectively from the Pacific as well as Asian states highlighted that (16%) and (8%) of Cambodian females were being physically threatened by her spouse and injured respectively [3, 27]. A survey which conducted on 6902 men of an Indian state of Uttar Pradesh in 1996, According to the report of the survey (45%) of married men accepted physical exploitation of their wives [30]. In Korea, the percentage of reported cases of physical aggression by husbands were 38% based on a survey of casual samples of females as well as in Thailand, the number of husbands who approved the physical exploitation of their wives minimum one-time after marriage was 619(20%) [31]. However, (25% to 70%) of Pakistani married females were being physically exploited by their husbands [22].

With respect to Pakistan reference, a cross-sectional study held on 400 married female belonging to a random ethnic group of five low socioeconomic society. It is true that the expansion of verbal violence was 97.5% & 97% by the husband as well as by laws respectively moreover in case of physical violence percentage through husband was 80% and bylaws, the percentage of physical abuse was 57.5% [29]. The context of the conducted study was the attitude of males against physical violence and it showed that 49 % males of Pakistan accepted to physically mistreat their wives. Hitting, slapping, and punching also included in physical exploitations of women. The researcher also highlighted that 55% of men faced physical aggression in childhood period. About 65% declared that they saw the physical exploitation of their mothers from their fathers and 46% have a belief that as a man they had authority to beat females [26]. Physical exploitation was the most general form of domestic aggression as well as its outcomes effects were deadly in nature specifically in the family. In Pakistan the most general kind of physical violence are, throwing of acid, beating, killing on the bases of honour and burning. In Pakistan the most critical kind of physical violence is burning of females, after Burning a woman is one of the most severe forms of physical abuse in Pakistan; females burning cases in the kitchen are common after getting marital status. According to report of IRIN (Integrated Regional Information Networks) in 2008 that PWA (Progressive Women Association) of Islamabad declare that almost 4000 burning cases of women are reported each year and such crime was

mostly done by in-laws or husband as well as the usual causes of burning are, penalty on minor crimes or not bringing huge amount of dowry. According to the Progressive Women Association, from March 1994 to March 2007 PWA collected the data of almost 8000 victims from just 03 Rawalpindi hospitals [32].

Due to cheapness and easy availability of sulphuric acid the cases of acid throwing is most usual, Acid throwing also comes in third-degree burns and irreversible damage to the women faces. According to the Human Right Commission Report of Pakistan in 2010 stated that a total number of domestic aggression cases which are reported were three seventy-three and among them, sixteen cases were of acid throwing [33]. Within two months of January and June 2014, the number of cases which were presented was fifteen in just Bahawalpur district with respect to report of IRIN published in 2005 [34]. According to a UNICEF report of 2000 in Bangladesh, approximately 200 cases of acid throwing reported every year in Bangladesh [27].

Emotional abuse is another kind of domestic aggression also called psychological abuse and its effects will remain in the victim's mind for a longer time as compared to physical aggression. The other categories of emotional exploitations are behaviour controlling, isolation and intimidating. The person who uses the method of psychological abuse often given threats of physical aggression [18]. According to UNICEF (2000), statement "extreme mental stress as well as living in a tense environment is most difficult and insufferable as compared to physical violence. Suicide, as well as suicide struggle, are major causes of extreme mental stress [27]. Studies finding shown that those females who are psychologically as well as emotionally victimized must be faced with other mental health problems like as low self-esteem, sexual dysfunction depression, anxiety, fear, eating as well as stress disorder with dissociation, flashbacks, obsessive self-harm, compulsive disorder etc. [3]. Anxiety and upset mental condition are requirements of physiological crime. A study carried out in three provinces of South Africa declared that the numbers of females become victims of emotional abuse were 51.4% [35]. Moreover, in Pakistan, 83.6 percent of the females who participated in study passes through the experience of emotional abuse in their life [23].

The other studies which held in Pakistan declared 46.9 to 79% percentage of Pakistani men involve in sex activity without intention of their wives.

CONCLUSION:

Domestic aggression is a worldwide issue. It apparent itself in spite of state, religion, region, custom as well as the main reason for not reported is, socially accepted by the community. Domestic aggression divided into four main forms, consisting of physical, sexual, verbal and emotional/psychological inhumane treatment and the most general form of domestic aggression is Verbal abuse. By different study analysis as well as literature review prove that entire forms of domestic violence present in Pakistan. On the World level, availability of written material on domestic aggression among women healthcare provider is very short as well as nothing reported from literature with respect to Pakistan context.

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